

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CONCEPT OF "TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES": ESSENCE AND CONTENT

Ulviyya Hajiyeva,

associate professor

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

ORCID No: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9612-6702>

Nazile Abdullazade

associate professor

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

ORCID No: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1829-7178>

Abstract

In the ever-developing and improving world, the educational system is also changing and aims to develop the moral and intellectual development of people, the ability to work with information, and the formation of creative and critical thinking. The main advantages of this system consist in the fact that the learner does not get it ready-made from the teacher, but in the process of his activity, and thus he has acquired the ability to turn information and problems into knowledge. As a result of the changing demands and needs of the society, the state and the citizen, new technologies entered the educational system.

The introduction of new learning technologies in general education schools began in the late 1990s. The transition to the Bologna education system, curriculum reform, new generation textbooks brought modern technologies to teaching. The use of active/interactive learning has accelerated the adoption of new technologies. First, despite the fact that serious successes in this field were not achieved, serious defects appeared in the teaching process, the scope of application of new technologies was expanding.

Keywords: teaching, technology, interactive, modern approach, integration.

Although the concept of teaching technology began to be developed in the scientific-methodical literature from the last decade of the 20th century, the ways and types of its use have been discussed more often in the last decade. This is primarily due to the fact that new teaching technologies are directly included in the teaching process and become one of the main attributes of the learning process. Over time, new technologies have been further improved, new ones have been developed and tested in classes. If you follow the pedagogical literature, it becomes clear that not all of these technologies are used or not all of them are successful. There are technologies and methods that teachers have accepted and applied very easily. There are technologies whose names are mentioned only in pedagogical literature today.

But what is technology in general? "Technology" consists of the Greek words *teshne* - art, profession, *logos* - science, teaching. As a pedagogical term, "the correct explanation of its essence requires first of all to look at it in a broad plan. Therefore, the concept of "technology" should be understood in both broad and narrow sense. Broadly speaking, this concept applies to all areas of human activity. That is, production of both material and spiritual wealth, as well as formation of moral values, corresponds to technology understood in a broad sense.

So, achieving something, what to use and how to use it to achieve the goal is the basis of technology. In short, the means used to achieve the goal, the methods used to activate these means, and all other types of activities that manifest themselves in this process together constitute the core, the essence of technology" [Didaktika, 1975:143].

We can understand the explanation of the term "Technology" in a broad sense as follows: "Technology, in general, is a scientifically and practically based activity system applied by people related to the study of the surrounding world and making relevant changes, the production of materials and the formation of a system of moral values" [Huseynoglu, 2003:9]

Soltan Huseynoghlu summarized the definitions given to the concept of "technology" in the pedagogical literature and showed the most used ones:

- pedagogical technology is systematic planning, activity and assessment methods applied to achieve more effective results in education, taking into account the entire learning process and knowledge acquisition, human and technical resources, their interaction;

- pedagogical technology is a system that expresses the functions of all components of the pedagogical process, which is built on a scientific basis, programmed within a certain time and space, and the intended results are achieved;

- pedagogical technology is the organization of the teacher's activity in such a way that all the actions included in this activity form a certain integrity and sequence, and their implementation results in expected achievements and has a prognostic character;

- pedagogical technology is a joint, mutual activity of teachers and students, carried out taking into account the principle of individuality. As a result of this activity, students master the state standard of education;

- pedagogical technology is the planned, sequential implementation of a pre-designed pedagogical process using optimal methods, principles and methods of action to achieve the set goals, etc.

From all these mentioned, we can conclude that the pedagogical technology is based on mutual cooperation in the learning process, it determines the organization of teaching and its successful completion using various methods and tools.

Effective application of pedagogical technologies, according to methodist scientists, depends on following their general principles. We can summarize these principles as follows:

- *educative principle*. In all eras, both traditional and curriculum teaching, the educative function has always been expected. Regardless of its nature and type, all technologies assume educativeness as a basis in the formation of personality. The main goal of the new teaching technologies is to cultivate the personality in the spirit of loyalty to the national ideology, moral and aesthetic values, and the ideology of Azerbaijaniism.

- *developing principle*. One of the teaching goals is developmental. Development is directly related to mental development and assumes the development of thinking and the formation of mental skills as a basis. For this, the student should be successful, reveal his individual capabilities and strength. In this case, it can succeed.

- *the principle of counter-relation with students*. The learner's understanding and assimilation of the material in the learning process emerges in the creation of the principle of counter-relation. This is based on the creation and permanence of multi-way counter-relation with students. How and at what level the student understands the learning material should be clear in the learning process. The student must return to the teacher what he heard from the teacher and what he learned at the same time. At this time, the teacher can monitor the student's development and also allows him to be informed about it.

- *principle of regular repetition*. Pedagogical experience shows that knowledge is ineffective if it is not applied, that is, it is forgotten. Studying the teaching material is one aspect of the work. It is known from experience that acquired knowledge is forgotten if it is not applied. Sometimes, depending on the situation, the application of knowledge is delayed. At this point, repetition is needed; the teacher should make room for repetition in each lesson by using different methods if possible. Any topic should be repeated, if not completely, but a certain part of it should be linked to a new topic. This should always be in the teacher's attention during the teaching process, should strengthen the acquired knowledge by connecting it with past knowledge.

- *the principle of optimal mental tension*. One of the points that the teacher should pay attention to when introducing new technologies in the educational process is that the educational material, the scope of the task and the level of mastery are accessible to the learners. As we know, the teaching material is low level, medium and hard according to the level of complexity. Although low-level tasks are easily completed by the student, they neither allow the student to develop nor allow the teacher to monitor his progress. When the task is too difficult, the student falls into psychological difficulties. For this, the teacher should choose such tasks and use such methods and tools as to be able to

monitor the student's development and create mutual cooperation with him.

- *the principle of maximum involvement of students in the teaching process (teaching activity)*. The introduction of new learning technologies also requires student engagement. Unlike traditional teaching, in interactive teaching, students should be more active and act as subjects. In order for the student to be active, the teacher should give him freedom and leave it up to him to complete the task. By acting as a facilitator, the teacher achieves the student's activity, which means the successful implementation of the developmental goal.

- *the principle of unification of teachers and students for a common goal*. The introduction of new technologies is based on the voluntary principle of teaching. Thus, the teacher cannot make the student accept anything in a planned way, there must be a type of activity based on the mutual consent of both sides - the teacher and the student. In the joint activity, the student solves the problem with both the teacher and his friends.

If we look at the essence of these principles, we will see that they are related to each other and ultimately serve to improve the quality of education.

Acquaintance with the scientific-methodical and pedagogical literature shows that teachers sometimes cannot use new technologies correctly, turn the lesson into entertainment or treat it as entertainment. Efficient noise in class, division into groups, etc., lead to defects. The reason for this can be attributed to the fact that some teachers are not aware of theoretical information and cannot "digest" new things. As a result, rather than achieving the goal set in the lesson, they strive for the mechanical execution of various operations, as if they are trying to demonstrate that they have implemented the requirements of the new technology.

This shows that no matter how much the technologies change and update, the teacher's methodology remains unchanged. The teacher adapts the new technology to his methodology and uses it, demonstrating that he accepts pedagogical innovation.

In conclusion, we can summarize the necessity of introducing new teaching technologies as follows:

- the development of science and technology also manifests itself in the teaching process;

- as in the content of teaching, there is a need to change pedagogical approaches, methods and technologies;

- Integration into the European education system enables the introduction of new teaching technologies;

- the rapid development of information and communication technologies necessitates the application of new technologies in teaching;

- an attempt to find a creative approach and solution to the events happening around in the age of scientific and technical progress.

New teaching technologies have given new content to learning for both teacher and student. Knowledge is no longer readily transmitted by the teacher, students try to acquire it by thinking and searching. The teacher is just a facilitator and guides and cooperates with the student in a mutual way. The teacher becomes creative and proactive, each lesson prompts him to conduct research, use additional

sources, different technical means. Thus, the purposeful activity of the teacher enables students to realize their potential.

Application of new teaching technologies also enriches students' activities. For example:

- acquires the opportunity and ability to conduct research on various sources;
- learns to work in a team, to cooperate;
- communication skills are formed;
- emotional-volitional qualities develop;
- acquires the ability to express his opinion honestly;
- acquires the ability to listen to the opinion of others, etc.

Experienced teachers do not forget the past experience on the basis of new technologies, they take the "good" from traditional teaching and synthesize it into interactive teaching. At the same time, it turns out that it is impossible to fully master the subject based only on new technologies, that is, on the independent research of the student. Because an independent approach to a subject he does not know sometimes creates confusion and distance from the subject in the student's imagination and thinking, which can eventually lead to the wrong conclusion. In this sense, the support and direction of the teacher is needed. Because no matter how independently the student thinks and searches, from a methodical point of view, he gives way to unsystematism, sparseness, and inappropriate "self-confidence". The teacher's intervention is definitely needed to systematize knowledge, generalize, and create connections.

Today, new teaching technologies have become an integral part of the educational system, based on the learning activity in accordance with the requirements of globalization. The teaching of subjects has taken a new direction. Increasing the students' mutual cooperation ability, creative and critical thinking and establishing communicative relations leads to activation in teaching.

Recent theoretical considerations have conducted various scientific studies based on the methodology of teaching subjects at the general secondary education level (grades V-IX), brought active-interactive teaching, which is the main function of constructive and dynamic management of teaching in a number of fields, to pedagogical science. In recent times, scientific theoretical considerations have introduced a new pedagogical perspective of active learning and ways of influencing a healthy psychological environment [Agayev, 2006:29].

L.A.Malkova, who divided the interactive teaching technologies in the modern lesson into theory, application and practice, explained the theoretical and methodological bases of the organization of this teaching [Малькова, 2014:26]. The teaching of the subject in general secondary education is presented with the application of didactic tools and lesson examples at each stage.

One of the main goals in active interactive teaching is to increase students' thinking skills, understanding of literary concepts in the context of high school, providing students with live communication conditions in the learning environment. These learning methods

include didactic games, brainstorming, question-and-answer, learning artistic algorithms, group work, role-playing, artistic stimulations, problem solving, and other contextual activities. The knowledge that the student will gain is further improved in these ways, it helps to increase cooperation, creativity, and critical thinking. Interactive methods reveal the facilitator role of the teacher and reflect the role of students in the learning center.

Mental activity in active teaching affects the correct development of the student's thinking and benefits the formation of free thinking. Understanding the themes and messages in the text, understanding the plot and describing the text are explained as important active skills [Yusifova, 2010]. Images and their interaction in a work of art can be better interpreted in the application of new learning technologies - collective discussion, groups, role-playing games and dialogues. At this time, the position of the author, the more prominent expression of the subtextual meaning of the work requires the inclusion of new teaching models in the teaching.

Fundamental changes in education and society have created a real basis for updating the content of the entire general education system, which is manifested in the development and application of new content elements, new educational technologies, and appeal to world pedagogical experience. The interactivity of the teaching also ensures the networking nature of the teaching, that is, the distribution of new information and technologies in social networks. Teachers and students can communicate worldwide and share important information and learning experience in social networks [Abbasov, 2005:24].

The introduction of new technologies in active teaching also changes the learning environment, which plays a major role in the formation of learners as personalities. The lesson is not enough to provide knowledge, it fully and comprehensively fulfills the requirements of emotionality, idealism, visibility, scientificity, intensity, integrativeness and the use of information and communication technologies. Various forms of organization of teaching - groups, pairs, individual types of work strengthen cognitive activity in students, increase understanding, differentiation strengthens motivation and empathy, and realizes reflective demonstrations. Lessons conducted in collective and group cooperation also regulate the communicative skills of students, regulate the dynamics of both oral and written speech.

The interactive teaching process encourages the teacher and students to learn together and facilitates the learning process. In an interactive teaching process involving teachers and students, the environment prepares learners for this teaching, encourages collaborative learning, and facilitates teaching. According to Russian educational psychologists A.E.Belkova and L.P.Lesnichenko, the introduction of new teaching technologies creates "freedom of action" in students, understood as a behavior [Belkova, 2015]

Today, the formation of skills to improve the ways of applying new teaching technologies is considered as the most important task of the modern teaching process.

References

1. Abbasov Ədalət, Balakışiyev Şahbaz, Əliyeva Bibixanım, Xudiyeva Gülarə, Süleymanova Afət (2005). Azərbaycan dili və ədəbiyyat. Metodika və təcrübə. – Bakı: “Orxan”. – 486 s.
2. Ağayev Əjdər (2006). Yeni təlim metod və texnologiyalarından istifadənin nəzəri və praktik məsələləri // Azərbaycan Respublikasının Təhsil Problemləri İnstitutunun Elmi əsərləri. – Bakı: №1. – s.29-44.
3. Həsənlı Bilal, Quliyev Əsgər, Hüseynoğlu Soltan (2003). Ədəbiyyat. Pilot məktəblərinin 6-cı sinfi üçün dərslik. – Bakı: “Çaşıoğlu”. – s.
4. Hüseynoğlu Soltan, Quliyev Əsgər, Həsənlı Bilal (2003) Ədəbiyyat. Pilot məktəblərinin 5-ci sinfi üçün dərslik. – Bakı: “Çaşıoğlu”. – s.
5. Yusifova S. (2010). Ədəbiyyat dərslərində fəal təlim üsullarından istifadə imkanları. //“Təhsil Problemləri” qəzeti. – 01-07, 14-21 iyun.
6. Дидактика средней школы (1975). Под редакцией М.А.Данилова и М.Н. Скаткина. Москва: – «Просвещение». – 195 стр.
7. Aktamovna A.D., Aktamovna A.X., Kuvondikkizi T.G. (2020). A non-traditional approach to organizing lessons. Bbk 83, 43.7.
8. Belkova A.E., Lesnichenko L.P. (2015) Interactive learning method on Russian language lessons as a way to increase cognitive activity students // Young-scientist. -No. 23. -P. 1068-1071. – URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/103/23947/>.
9. Малькова Л.А. (2014). Что такое методическая разработка и требования, предъявляемые к ней. – Москва: ГАПОУ МОК им. В.Талалихина. – 26 с.